

Directional Macroeconomic Forecasting: Robustness of KNN versus Flexibility of ANN and SVM on Limited Data

Tarek Bahaa Aly¹, Ahmed El-Masry²

Abstract

In this paper, we predicted the directional movement (up or down) of five macroeconomic variables: the equity market (EQUITY), foreign exchange rate (FX), central bank policy rate (POLRATE), GDP growth rate (GDP), and inflation rate (INF), using K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), and Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifiers, compared with a logistic regression model included as a linear benchmark. The analysis was conducted on monthly data from eight diverse markets across different geographical regions (US, UK, Mexico, Brazil, Egypt, South Africa, Indonesia, China) over forecast horizons of 1, 3, and 6 months. Our aim was to compare the predictive performance of these three fundamentally different classifiers and identify common patterns in macroeconomic variable behavior. We found that the standard KNN classifier significantly outperformed SVM and ANN, achieving the highest average out-of-sample directional accuracy. Our analysis revealed that the optimal number of neighbors, K , did not materially affect out-of-sample accuracy and remained relatively stable across forecast horizons. Feature importance analysis showed that KNN relied on a few strong signals, such as the yield curve level, while SVM and ANN distributed importance weights more broadly. The highest average prediction accuracies were achieved by the equity market and FX, while the US and China recorded the strongest country-level performance. In addition, inflation and the equity market exhibited the highest predictive power. Our results demonstrated the continued value of simple, robust models like KNN for macroeconomic directional forecasting, particularly when compared to more complex models such as SVM and ANN on limited panel data.

Keywords: Classifier, ANN, SVM, KNN, Equity Market, Foreign Exchange Rate, Inflation, Policy Rate, GDP, Feature Importance

JEL codes: C32, C45, C53, E37

¹ Independent Researcher, Cairo, Egypt. ORCID ID: 0009-0001-1380-2630. Email: tarekbahaaaly@gmail.com

² Prince Sultan University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. Email: aelmasry@psu.edu.sa

1 Introduction

Machine learning models are increasingly being developed across a wide range of industries, capable of analyzing complex datasets and providing solutions to a wide range of users. Machine learning tools enable institutions to identify lucrative opportunities and potential threats. New techniques in this field are evolving rapidly and expanding the application of machine learning in almost all industries such as healthcare, sales, consumer behavior, e-commerce, transportation, and financial services. In this study, we predicted the directional movement of five macroeconomic variables, namely the equity market (EQUITY), foreign exchange rate (FX), central bank policy rate (POLRATE), GDP growth rate (GDP), and inflation rate (INF), using three fundamental classifiers: K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and a feedforward Artificial Neural Network (ANN), compared with logistic regression as a linear benchmark, to place the machine learning results in an econometric context. This research was conducted on the following markets: the United States (US), United Kingdom (UK), Mexico (MEX), Brazil (BRA), Egypt (EGP), South Africa (SAF), Indonesia (IND), and China (CHI), over three forecast horizons: 1, 3, and 6 months.

Most existing studies on macroeconomic variable prediction focus on selecting the single best-performing model for a specific market, often without directly comparing fundamentally different classes of classifiers on the same multi-country panel. As a result, it remains unclear whether the added complexity of models like SVM or ANN yields meaningful gains in directional accuracy over simpler, more transparent methods like KNN, and which economic signals each model actually relies on beyond own persistence. This study contributed to the literature by providing a direct comparison of these three model classes on a diverse multi-country macro dataset. To ensure we were measuring only the unique forecasting contribution of yield curve factors and the other macroeconomic variables, we intentionally excluded any autoregressive lags of the predicted variable. Furthermore, we conducted a thorough behavioral analysis of the K hyperparameter in KNN and a feature importance analysis for all models to understand which economic signals drive their predictions. To the best of our knowledge, weighted KNN (wKNN) has not previously been applied to macroeconomic variable prediction, and its application here is one of the contributions of this study.

2 Literature Review

The literature on macroeconomic directional prediction has increasingly turned toward machine learning techniques, yet relatively few studies provide a direct comparison between simple non-parametric methods and more complex neural network approaches on the same multi-country panel. We have presented, in this literature review, academic work on the topic of macroeconomic variable prediction in terms of model development and performance.

Classifiers have proven to be reliable and more stable than regression models for predicting the direction of macroeconomic variables, as it is often more meaningful to forecast the cycle of the economy rather than a continuous value (Estrella et al., 2003). Academic scholars have noted the superior prediction accuracy of classifiers over linear statistical techniques. For example, the results of Priambodo et al. (2019) showed that their classifier was able to predict GDP using a small dataset better than multiple linear regression models. In addition, Maccarrone et al. (2021) found that classifier-based predictions performed better than traditional linear models. Among these classifiers, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) is a simple and intuitive technique that has been successfully employed for time series prediction. Ballings et al. (2015) used KNN to predict stock market direction, Rodriguez-Vargas (2020) used it to predict inflation, and Maccarrone et al. (2021) used it for GDP forecasting.

Support Vector Machines (SVM) have been widely applied in directional forecasting of financial and macroeconomic variables, including stock market movements, exchange rates, and commodity prices. SVM with a radial basis function (RBF) kernel provides an intermediate level of model complexity between the simple non-parametric KNN and more complex neural architectures, such as ANN. Unlike KNN, which relies solely on local similarity and majority voting, SVM introduces greater flexibility by mapping the input features into a higher-dimensional space through kernel transformations, allowing it to capture non-linear relationships while maintaining good generalization properties even with relatively limited data (Cortes & Vapnik, 1995; Kim, 2003).

On the other hand, Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have become a focal point in academic research because of their non-linear capabilities and flexible design architectures (McNelis, 2005). Tkacz (2001) used an ANN to forecast Canadian GDP growth, finding that its non-linear nature provided an edge over linear models for longer-term horizons. Bal and Demir (2017) used ANNs to forecast exchange rates, while Jahn (2018) used them to predict the GDP

of 15 countries, with results more accurate than corresponding linear models. Hybrid models and ensemble methods, which combine multiple machine learning techniques, have also emerged and often outperformed traditional ANNs (Nti et al., 2020; Alotaibi, 2021).

Our literature review confirmed that most academic studies aimed to select the single best-performing model for a specific market. Our research differed by providing a direct comparison of the straightforward KNN approach with SVM and the more complex ANN architecture on a diverse multi-country macro dataset, assessing whether the added complexity was justified, with particular attention to feature importance and the behavior of the K hyperparameter.

3 Methodology

3.1 Data Methodology

Our analysis was conducted on monthly data from 2006 to 2019, capturing different economic cycles, including the 2008-2009 mortgage crisis and the 2012-2013 European recession. All observations were collected on a monthly basis, except for the GDP growth rates which were on a quarterly basis. Hence, we transformed the GDP frequency from quarterly to monthly using cubic splines, as this method has been shown to perform well in such transformations (Kaya, 2013).

For the prediction task, we defined the binary classification target, $y_t^{(h)}$, for each macroeconomic variable as an indicator of its future direction over a forecast horizon $h \in \{1, 3, 6\}$ months:

Equation 1 Binary classification target for directional movement

$$y_t^{(h)} = 1_{(x_{t+h} > x_t)} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x_{t+h} > x_t \text{ (upward movement)} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise (downward or no movement)} \end{cases}$$

where x_t is the value of the macroeconomic variable at time t . For each country, the data was chronologically split, preserving the time-series order, into a training set (first 70% of observations) and a testing set (remaining 30% of observations). All input features were normalized using the z-score methodology, where the mean and standard deviation were calculated solely from the training data set and applied to both training and testing sets to prevent look-ahead bias.

The input features for our models consisted of the three latent factors from the yield curve (Level, Slope, and Curvature) extracted via Principal Component Analysis (PCA), in addition to the rest of the macroeconomic variables. To isolate cross-variable predictive power and avoid self-predictive autocorrelation, we excluded the autoregressive lags of the target variable itself from the feature set (AR_LAGS = 0). This choice imposes a stricter test by removing the strong persistence typically present in monthly macro series, allowing us to better evaluate the genuine incremental contribution of yield curve latent factors and other cross-variables.

3.2 KNN Classifier

We employed the KNN algorithm to predict the directional movement of macroeconomic variables. KNN is a non-parametric, instance-based learning method that has been extensively applied in various fields, including economics and finance, due to its simplicity and effectiveness (Harrison, 2018; Priambodo et al., 2019; Maccarrone et al., 2021). The training dataset was used to establish the feature space. For each point in the testing set, the algorithm computed its distance to all points in the training set. We used the Euclidean distance as the distance metric, defined as:

Equation 2 Euclidean distance

$$d(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}) = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m (p_j - q_j)^2}$$

where \mathbf{p} is the feature vector of the test point, \mathbf{q} is the feature vector of a training point, and m is the number of features. The distances are then ranked, and the K smallest distances (nearest neighbors) are selected (Fiori, 2020). The final classification for the test point is determined by a majority vote among its K neighbors:

Equation 3 KNN classification via majority vote

$$\hat{y} = \text{mode} \left(\{y^{(i)}\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}_K} \right)$$

Where \mathcal{N}_K is the set of indices of the K nearest neighbors and $y^{(i)}$ is the class label (0 or 1) of the i -th neighbor.

The optimal value of K was selected from a range of 1 to 100, based on the maximization of the out-of-sample prediction accuracy on the testing set. The prediction accuracy was defined as the proportion of correct directional forecasts.

3.3 Weighted KNN (wKNN)

As a variant, we implemented a Weighted KNN (wKNN) approach, where the contribution of each neighbor to the majority vote was weighted by the inverse of its distance to the test point (Zhao & Chen, 2016). The prediction is then determined by:

Equation 4 Weighted KNN classification

$$\hat{y} = \arg \max_{c \in \{0,1\}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}_K} w_i \cdot \mathbf{1}(y^{(i)} = c), \quad \text{where } w_i = \frac{1}{d(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}_i) + \epsilon}$$

and ϵ is a small constant to prevent division by zero. This method gives more influence to closer neighbors, reducing the impact of more distant ones. To the best of our knowledge, the application of wKNN to macroeconomic variable prediction is one of the contributions of this study.

3.4 Analysis of K: Relationship with Accuracy and Forecast Horizon

Following the model estimation, we conducted a behavioral analysis of the optimal K . To formally test the relationships observed, we estimated two sets of ordinary least squares (OLS) regressions. The first set tested the relationship between the forecast horizon and the optimal number of neighbors:

$$K_{\text{optimal}} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{Horizon} + \epsilon$$

The second set tested whether the optimal K itself had a significant effect on the out-of-sample prediction accuracy:

$$\text{Test Accuracy} = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 \cdot K_{\text{optimal}} + \nu$$

These regressions were performed for each target variable individually and for the combined dataset (Boeck & Feldkircher, 2021). The statistical significance of the coefficients β_1 and γ_1 was assessed to determine, respectively, whether longer forecast horizons required a different K and whether the choice of K materially affected predictive performance.

3.5 SVM Classifier

To provide a more comprehensive comparison across varying levels of model complexity, we included a SVM classifier with a radial basis function (RBF) kernel as an intermediate non-linear classifier. Positioned between the simple, instance-based KNN and the highly flexible ANN, SVM offers greater flexibility than KNN through kernel-based non-linear mapping while remaining more interpretable and less data intensive than deep neural architectures.

SVM is widely recognized for its strong theoretical foundations and effectiveness in binary classification tasks (Cortes & Vapnik, 1995; Schölkopf & Smola, 2002). The model seeks to find the hyperplane that maximizes the margin between the two classes while allowing for some misclassifications through a soft-margin formulation. Mathematically, the optimization problem can be expressed as:

Equation 5 SVM soft-margin optimization problem

$$\min_{w,b,\xi} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i$$

subject to

$$y_i(w^T \phi(x_i) + b) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \quad \xi_i \geq 0, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n$$

where w is the weight vector, b is the bias, ξ_i are the slack variables that allow for misclassifications, C is the regularization parameter that controls the trade-off between maximizing the margin and minimizing classification errors, and $\phi(x)$ represents the feature map induced by the kernel function.

For the radial basis function (RBF) kernel used in this study, the kernel function is given by:

Equation 6 Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel

$$K(x_i, x_j) = \exp(-\gamma \|x_i - x_j\|^2)$$

where $\gamma > 0$ is a parameter that controls the width of the kernel.

The hyperparameters of the SVM model were selected based on standard practices in SVM literature for financial and macroeconomic forecasting. We used the radial basis function (RBF) kernel, which is the most commonly adopted kernel in this domain due to its ability to capture non-linear patterns effectively (Kim, 2003; Huang et al., 2005). A grid search was performed over the regularization parameter C with values [0.1, 1, 10, 100, 1000] to control the trade-off between margin maximization and classification error. The kernel parameter γ was set to its default ‘scale’ value in scikit-learn, which is a recommended starting point that often yields robust performance on standardized data. These choices were guided by common methodological approaches in the literature and preliminary sensitivity tests on the dataset.

3.6 ANN Classifier

We developed a feedforward ANN as a comparative classifier. ANNs are powerful models capable of approximating complex non-linear functions, and have been successfully applied to forecast various macroeconomic variables (Tkacz, 2001; Bal & Demir, 2017; Jahn, 2018). Our network topology is a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) designed for binary classification.

The ANN classifier structure was subdivided into three layers: first, an **input layer** with the number of nodes equal to the number of input features. Second, **one hidden** layer was used. Following most academic literature in this domain, a single hidden layer is sufficient to approximate complex non-linear functions for forecasting macroeconomic variables. The number of **hidden nodes/neurons** was chosen to be twelve (12), following a sensitivity analysis conducted on the number of hidden neurons and hidden layers, where we tested between eight and sixty hidden neurons (8-60) and from one to two hidden layers (1-2). The selected hyperparameters yielded the highest average test accuracy results. The **activation function** used in the hidden layer was the **hyperbolic tangent (tanh)**, defined as:

Equation 7 Hyperbolic tangent (tanh) activation function

$$\phi(z) = \tanh(z) = \frac{e^z - e^{-z}}{e^z + e^{-z}}$$

This S-shaped tanh function squashes the input to a range between -1 and 1 and is symmetric around zero.

In the **output layer**, a **single node** with the sigmoid activation function was selected, defined as:

Equation 8 Sigmoid activation function for binary probability output

$$\sigma(z) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}}$$

The sigmoid function squashes the output to a range between 0 and 1, which can be interpreted as the probability of an upward movement (class 1). The final classification is $\hat{y}=1$ if $\sigma(z) \geq 0.5$, and $\hat{y}=0$ otherwise.

The network is trained to minimize the **binary cross-entropy** loss function, which for a single observation is:

Equation 9 Binary cross-entropy loss function

$$L(y, \hat{y}) = - [y \log(\hat{y}) + (1 - y) \log(1 - \hat{y})]$$

where y is the true label and \hat{y} is the predicted probability. The total loss is the average over all observations in the training batch. We used the **Adam** optimizer (Kingma & Ba, 2017) with a fixed learning rate and gradient clipping to update the network weights. L2 regularization (weight decay) was applied to the weights of the hidden layers to mitigate overfitting, a common concern when working with relatively small macroeconomic datasets.

3.7 Logistic Regression

As a linear benchmark, we estimated a logistic regression model for each country–target–horizon combination using the same features and chronological 70/30 train-test split. The model takes the standard logistic form:

Equation 10 Logistic regression model

$$P(y_{t+h} = 1 | \mathbf{x}_t) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-(\beta_0 + \beta' \mathbf{x}_t))}$$

where y_{t+h} is the binary indicator of an upward movement over horizon h , and \mathbf{x}_t includes the three yield curve latent factors and the remaining macroeconomic variables. Feature importance for the logistic regression was computed using permutation importance, consistent with the approach applied to KNN and ANN, and normalized to sum to 100% per target.

3.8 Feature Importance

To assess the relative contribution of each predictor, we employed two different feature importance techniques depending on the model type.

For ANN, we computed a gradient-based sensitivity measure. Specifically, we calculated the absolute value of the partial derivative of the model's output probability with respect to each input feature and averaged these values across all test observations. The resulting scores were normalized to sum to 100% for each target variable. Formally, the importance of feature j is given by:

Equation 11 Gradient-based feature importance metric

$$I_j = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \frac{\partial \hat{y}_i}{\partial x_{i,j}} \right|$$

where \hat{y}_i is the predicted probability for observation i , $x_{i,j}$ is the value of feature j , and N is the number of test samples (Simonyan et al., 2014).

For KNN, SVM, and logistic regression models, we used permutation importance. This model-agnostic approach measures the decrease in prediction accuracy when the values of a particular feature are randomly shuffled in the test set. The resulting importance scores were also normalized to sum to 100% for each target variable. This allowed consistent comparison of variable contributions across all three models (Breiman, 2001; Fisher, Rudin, & Dominici, 2019).

4 Empirical Results

4.1 K of KNN versus the Prediction Accuracy and the Forecasted Horizon

In this section, we studied the relationship between the number of neighbors (K) in the KNN classifier, the prediction accuracy, and the forecast horizon, in order to understand how the choice of the number of neighbors (K) affects predictive performance, and forecast horizons in the KNN classifier.

Panel (a) All K vs Average of Test Accuracy

Panel (b) Best K vs Test Accuracy

Figure 1 K vs Accuracy

The analysis began with an examination of how test-set accuracy varied with different values of K . Figure 1 presented two complementary views of this relationship, with all values averaged across the eight countries and five target variables. In Figure 1(a) the average test accuracy was plotted against all possible values of K from 1 to 100. The figure revealed an

irregular pattern in which accuracy rose for very small values of K, then dropped, and rose again at higher values of K. This pattern indicated that small numbers of neighbors were often sufficient to achieve the best accuracy and that increasing K further did not produce a systematic improvement in predictive performance.

Figure 1(b) illustrated the best-performing (optimal) K selected for each country-target-horizon combination. Here, we observed a much flatter relationship. For each optimal K, test accuracy remained relatively stable across the range of selected K values (roughly 0.60–0.65). Taken together, the two panels of Figure 1 showed that gains from increasing K occurred mainly in the low-K region, while further increases beyond the optimal point brought little or no additional benefit. Hence, there was no clear relationship between K and test accuracy.

Figure 2 Best K vs Horizons

The behavior of the optimal K with respect to the forecast horizon was illustrated in Figure 2. The plot revealed only modest variation: the average optimal K fluctuated between 20 and 24 across the 1-, 3-, and 6-month horizons, with no clear increasing or decreasing trend. A more detailed breakdown of the average optimal K vs variables, countries and horizons was provided in Appendix Table 1. Appendix Table 1.A (by forecast horizon) confirmed the stability seen in Figure 2: the mean optimal K stood at 23 for the 1-month horizon, 24 for the 3-month horizon, and 20 for the 6-month horizon. From this table, we concluded that the forecast horizon had only a limited influence on the required number of neighbors. Appendix Table 1.B (by target variable) revealed modest differences across economic variables: inflation required the highest average K (27), followed by the policy rate (25) and GDP (24), while FX required the lowest (16). This suggested that more volatile series such as inflation needed a larger neighborhood to

smooth noise, whereas FX appeared easier to predict with fewer neighbors. Appendix Table 1.C (by country) highlighted cross-country heterogeneity, with Brazil requiring a substantially higher average K (38) than the United States (16), for example.

To formally test the relationships observed visually, we estimated two sets of linear regressions. The first set regressed the optimal K on the forecast horizon (in months). The second set regressed test-set accuracy on the optimal K. Results appear in Appendix Table 2. For the horizon-to-K regression, only inflation showed a statistically significant (negative) relationship (coefficient = -4.10 , $p = 0.029$), implying that longer forecast horizons required slightly fewer neighbors when predicting inflation. All other coefficients (including the combined specification) are statistically insignificant. For the K-to-accuracy regression, only policy rate and equity market yielded a marginally significant positive coefficient, while the remaining variables, and the combined specification across all data, showed no statistically significant relationship ($p > 0.10$). These findings are fully consistent with our earlier results and confirmed that, once the optimal K is selected, further changes in K do not materially affect out-of-sample directional accuracy.

Overall, the analysis in this section revealed three main conclusions. First, the relationship between K and test-set accuracy was weak and irregular (Figure 1(a)), with small values of K frequently delivering the best performance. Second, the optimal K itself remained relatively stable across forecast horizons and showed only mild heterogeneity across target variables and countries (Figure 2 and Appendix Table 1). Third, once the optimal K was selected, further changes in K did not materially affect out-of-sample directional accuracy (Appendix Table 2). These patterns confirmed the robustness of the KNN framework in this macroeconomic setting.

4.2 Prediction Results

In this section, we evaluate the out-of-sample directional prediction accuracy of KNN, wKNN, SVM, and ANN, with logistic regression included as a linear benchmark. Table 3 in the Appendix reported the average test-set accuracy for each classifier, broken down by target variable (Table 3.A), country (Table 3.B), and forecast horizon (Table 3.C). We also reported the standard deviation (σ) of predictions to assess the stability of each model.

As shown in table 3.A, KNN classifier achieved the highest average directional accuracy across all countries and variables (65.25%), followed by wKNN (63.22%), SVM (60.55%), ANN

(53.05%), and logistic regression (52.55%). These accuracy levels were obtained without including autoregressive lags of the target variable. Consequently, the reported accuracies represent a more demanding test of the models' ability to extract predictive information from yield curve factors and other macroeconomic variables. The inclusion of SVM and logistic regression further confirmed that KNN outperformed both a popular non-linear kernel method and a standard linear benchmark, as well as the more complex ANN. Moreover, SVM was the most consistent approach with the lowest sigma of predictions among the variables (3.91%), followed by KNN (7.25%). The equity market recorded the strongest performance across all classifiers, reaching a maximum of 76% under the standard KNN, and an average among all models and countries of 67.5%. This was followed by FX reaching a maximum of 68.33% for KNN and an average among all models and countries of 63.52%. The superior predictability of EQUITY and FX directions was economically intuitive: both variables are directly influenced by yield-curve factors and macroeconomic conditions that are relatively persistent at the monthly frequency, allowing even simple neighborhood-based methods to capture directional signals effectively.

Table 3.B highlighted clear cross-country heterogeneity. The US achieved the highest average accuracy, while developing countries such as Brazil and Egypt generally recorded lower performance. This pattern was consistent with the higher quality and lower noise of macroeconomic and financial data in developed markets, which facilitates more reliable directional forecasts. KNN also showed the lowest prediction variability across countries (sigma = 3.95%), and China had the most stable variables' predictions, with the lowest sigma per country (3.52%).

Table 3.C examined the effect of the forecast horizon. As one would expect, both KNN and wKNN delivered their highest average accuracy at the shortest (1-month) horizon (66% and 64%, respectively), with accuracy declining modestly for longer horizons. In contrast, ANN achieved its highest average accuracy at the 6-month horizon (54%). This reversal suggested that the neural network was able to extract longer-term non-linear relationships embedded in the yield-curve factors and macroeconomic variables, relationships that become more apparent only over extended horizons, whereas the non-parametric KNN performed best when the signal was strongest in the near term. The 6-month prediction sigma, for all models, was the lowest (5.04%) implying that macroeconomic variables are more stable in the long run.

Overall, the results in this section showed that the KNN classifier outperformed the weighted variant, the intermediate SVM, logistic regression benchmark, and the more complex ANN in terms of average directional accuracy. KNN exhibited comparatively strong stability and consistency among the evaluated models, with the lowest prediction sigma on average. The equity market and FX had the highest prediction accuracy amongst all variables. China exhibited the most stable predictive performance across variables, as reflected in the lowest per-country prediction sigma. The relatively modest size of the monthly macro panel, likely limited ANN's ability to learn robust non-linear patterns without overfitting, while KNN, being non-parametric and instance-based, proved more robust to the noisy and limited data typical of developing and developed-market macro series. These findings suggest that simple nearest-neighbor methods could remain effective tools for macroeconomic directional forecasting under limited-data settings.

4.3 Feature Importance Results

Table 4 in the Appendix presents the average normalized feature importance (in percent) across all horizons and countries for each target variable. Tables 4.A to 4.D report the results for KNN, ANN, SVM, and logistic regression, respectively. Figure 3 provides a visual comparison of normalized feature importance by model, while Figure 4 shows the average importance weights per variable across all models.

The feature importance metrics derived from KNN and logistic regression models warranted particular attention. Under both models, several variables received zero importance. For KNN, this occurred because small changes in those variables did not affect the majority vote among the nearest neighbors and therefore carried no weight in the final prediction. For logistic regression, zero importance arose when a variable had no discriminatory power in the linear decision boundary (i.e., its coefficient was effectively zero after fitting). In contrast, ANN assigned strictly positive importance to every variable for every target.

KNN concentrated predictive power in a few dominant variables. LEVEL was the most important predictor overall, contributing 32% to INF predictions and 25% to GDP predictions. SVM and ANN presented a markedly different picture. Predictive power was distributed more evenly, with EQUITY, GDP, POLRATE and INF emerging as the strongest contributors. This suggests that KNN feature importance identified a few strong signals, like LEVEL, and gave

them high weight, while SVM and ANN feature importance was more spread out, assigning positive weight to almost all variables, but no single variable dominated as strongly as in the KNN model. The substantial difference in feature importance patterns was expected by design: KNN is a simple “nearest neighbor” method (focusing on exact matches), while SVM and ANN are complex models that learn many interactions at once. In fact, SVM and ANN models did not produce “better” feature importance, they gave different feature importance weights, more balanced and positive, but it came at the cost of lower prediction accuracy. In other words, KNN is simpler, more robust on this small/noisy dataset and delivered higher accuracy by focusing on the strongest signals. SVM and ANN found more subtle patterns but failed to translate them into better predictions, resulting in more even (but less decisive) importance scores.

Figure 3 Normalized Feature Importance by Model

Presented in figure 3 are the normalized feature importance (%) by model, averaged across all targets and horizons. KNN showed highly concentrated importance on a few dominant variables (particularly the yield curve LEVEL), as previously mentioned, whereas SVM and ANN distributed weights more evenly across predictors. Logistic regression exhibited an intermediate pattern.

Figure 4 Average of Feature Importance for all Models

Presented in figure 4 are the averages of feature importance weights per variable for all models. The highest average contributing variable was inflation (20%), followed by the equity market (17%), the central bank’s policy rate (14%), and the yield curve level (13%). This finding was consistent with academic literature, where there is an association between inflation, yield curve parallel shift (LEVEL), and central bank policy. In other words, higher inflationary pressures will trigger a rise in the yield curve in the form of a parallel shift (the Level), prompting the central bank to hike its policy rate (Ang & Piazzesi, 2003; Djuranovik, 2014; Shareef & Shijin, 2017). Furthermore, the equity market’s relation to other macroeconomic variables was significant (17%). Consistent with academic literature, Ahmed et al. (2017) proved that there is evidence of Causality from the interest rate to the stock market, in addition, Fromentin (2022) found evidence of a causality from industrial production to the stock market. Furthermore, Suhaibu, Harvey, & Amidu (2017) found that stock markets are affected by their respective monetary policies through interest rates, and in the long term this relation is bidirectional. In fact, the equity market plays a pivotal role in the economy, as it was found to be a leading indicator of economic activity (Plihal, 2016).

Overall, KNN relied heavily on a few dominant signals (yield curve LEVEL) and achieved higher directional accuracy, while SVM and ANN distributed importance more broadly but delivered lower accuracy. The logistic regression benchmark showed an intermediate pattern, further supporting that simpler methods can be more robust on this type of data. Additionally,

these results reinforced the value of yield-curve and macro information for directional forecasting while highlighting the trade-off between the robustness of simple nearest-neighbor methods and the richer but harder-to-realize interactions captured by neural networks on limited macro data. For policy makers and investors, the variables with the highest predictive power were the inflation, the equity market, the policy rate and the yield curve level. The fact that inflation emerged as the variable with the highest feature importance and predictive power suggests a paradigm shift, emphasizing the paramount importance of inflation control relative to economic growth promotion. The equity market ranked second in predictive importance, functioning as a leading indicator of macroeconomic activity and underscoring its instrumental role in the transmission of economic information.

5 Conclusion

This study predicted the directional movement of five macroeconomic variables: the equity market, foreign exchange rate, central bank policy rate, GDP growth rate, and inflation rate, using KNN, SVM, and ANN classifiers. The analysis was conducted on data from eight diverse markets across different geographical regions (US, UK, Mexico, Brazil, Egypt, South Africa, Indonesia, China) over three forecast horizons (1, 3, and 6 months).

Our empirical results led to several key conclusions. The straightforward KNN approach was able to outperform more complex models such as SVM and ANN in terms of average accuracy across countries and variables, as well as in the maximum accuracy achieved. This suggested that for monthly macroeconomic panel data, often noisy and of limited length, the robustness and simplicity of non-parametric instance-based learning offered significant advantages over highly parameterized approaches. KNN also generated the most stable predictions, as reflected in its relatively low prediction variability, followed by SVM. Additionally, China had the most stable variables' predictions, with the lowest sigma per country. Our analysis of the K hyperparameter revealed that the optimal number of neighbors K had no statistically significant effect on predictive accuracy and remained relatively stable across forecast horizons. The feature importance analysis provided critical insights into the predictive power of the variables. For the KNN, the predictive power was highly concentrated on a few dominant signals, with the yield curve level being the most important predictor overall. In contrast, SVM and ANN feature importance weights were more evenly distributed. For

policymakers and investors, inflation, equity markets, the policy rate, and the yield curve level emerged as the most powerful predictors. The emergence of inflation as the top contributor to predictive performance may signal a paradigm shift, elevating price stability above growth promotion as the paramount macroeconomic priority. The equity market ranked second in predictive contribution, serving as a forward-looking barometer of economic activity and affirming its instrumental function in the aggregation and transmission of anticipatory economic information.

Several limitations of this study should be acknowledged. By excluding autoregressive lags of the dependent variable, our analysis provided a cleaner assessment of the incremental predictive content embedded in yield curve and macroeconomic variables. While this choice might have moderated the absolute accuracy levels, it strengthened the interpretation of our feature importance results and the robustness-flexibility trade-off between KNN, SVM, and ANN. In addition, the moderate sample size could constrain the ability of complex models like ANNs to generalize, a limitation that may be less binding in higher-frequency or longer-span datasets. Furthermore, our binary classification framework discards information about the magnitude of movements, which could be relevant for certain risk management applications. Future research could expand this work by incorporating hybrid models that combine KNN with dimension reduction techniques or ensemble methods, potentially improving accuracy while retaining interpretability.

6 References

- Nti, I., Adekoya, A., & Weyori, B. (2020). A comprehensive evaluation of ensemble learning for stock-market prediction. *Journal of Big Data*, 7, 20. Retrieved from <https://journalofbigdata.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40537-020-00299-5>
- Ahmed, R., Vveinhardt, J., Streimikiene, D., & Fayyaz, M. (2017). Multivariate Granger Causality Between Macro Variables and KSE 100 Index: Evidence from Johansen cointegration and Toda & Yamamoto Causality. *Economic Research*, 30(1), 1497–1521. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1331677X.2017.1340176>
- Alotaibi, S. (2021). Ensemble technique with optimal feature selection for Saudi stock market prediction: A novel hybrid red deer-grey algorithm. *IEEE Access*, 9. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350903773_Ensemble_Technique_With_Optim

al_Feature_Selection_for_Saudi_Stock_Market_Prediction_A_Novel_Hybrid_Red_Deer-Grey_Algorithm

- Ang , A., & Piazzesi, M. (2003). A no-arbitrage vector autoregression of term structure dynamics with macroeconomics and latent variables. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 50(4), 745-787. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0304393203000321>
- Bal, C., & Demir, S. (2017). A comparative study of artificial neural network models for forecasting USD/EUR-GBP-JPY-NOK exchange rates. *Journal of Emerging Issues in Economics, Finance and Banking*, 6(2), 2248-2259. Retrieved from http://globalbizresearch.org/economics/images/files/87431_N706_JEIEFB_Cagatay%20Bal_Serdar%20Demir.pdf
- Ballings, M., Poel, D.-V.-d., Hespeels, N., & Gryp, R. (2015). Evaluating multiple classifiers for stock price direction prediction. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 42(20), 7046-7056. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0957417415003334>
- Breiman , L. (2001). Random forests. *Machine Learning*, 45(1), 5–32. Retrieved from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1023/A:1010933404324>
- Cortes, C., & Vapnik, V. (1995). Support-vector networks. *Machine Learning*, 20(3), 273–297. Retrieved from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/BF00994018>
- Djuranovik, L. (2014). The Indonesian Macroeconomy And The Yield Curve: A Dynamic Latent Factor Approach. *Journal of Asian Economics*, 34, 1-15. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1049007814000396>
- Estrella, A., Rodrigues, A., & Schich, S. (2003). How stable is the predictive power of the yield curve? evidence from germany and the united states. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 85(3), 629-644. Retrieved from <https://direct.mit.edu/rest/article/85/3/629/57434/How-Stable-is-the-Predictive-Power-of-the-Yield>
- Fiori, L. (2020). *Distance metrics and K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN)*. Retrieved from Medium.com: <https://medium.com/@luigi.fiori.lf0303/distance-metrics-and-k-nearest-neighbor-knn-1b840969c0f4>
- Fisher, A., Rudin, C., & Dominici, F. (2019). All models are wrong, but many are useful: Learning a variable's importance by studying an entire class of prediction models simultaneously. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 20(177), 1–81. Retrieved from <https://jmlr.org/papers/v20/18-760.html>
- Fromentin, V. (2022). Time-varying causality between stock prices and macroeconomic fundamentals: Connection or disconnection? *Finance Research Letters*, 49. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S154461232200304X>

- Harrison, O. (2018). *Machine Learning Basics with the K-Nearest Neighbors Algorithm*. Retrieved from Medium.com: <https://medium.com/data-science/machine-learning-basics-with-the-k-nearest-neighbors-algorithm-6a6e71d01761>
- Huang, W., Nakamori, Y., & Wang, S. (2005). Forecasting stock market movement direction with support vector machine. *Computers & Operations Research*, 32(10), 2513–2522. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0305054804000681>
- Jahn, M. (2018). Artificial neural network regression models: Predicting GDP growth. *Hamburg Institute of International Economics Working Paper*. Retrieved from https://update.hwwi.org/fileadmin/hwwi/Publikationen/Publikationen_PDFs_2018/HWWI_ResearchPaper_185.pdf
- Kaya, H. (2013). The yield curve and macroeconomic variables in the presence of policy change: Evidence from Turkey. *Economic Modelling*, 32, 100-107. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S026499931300045X>
- Kim, K. (2003). Financial time series forecasting using support vector machines. *Neurocomputing*, 55, 307–319. Retrieved from <https://c.mql5.com/forextd/forum/35/kim2003.pdf>
- Kingma, D., & Ba, J. (2017). *Adam: A Method for Stochastic Optimization*. arXiv:1412.6980. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/1412.6980>
- Maccarrone, G., Morelli, G., & Spadaccini, S. (2021). GDP forecasting: machine learning, linear or autoregression. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*, 4. Retrieved from <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/frai.2021.757864/full>
- McNelis, P. (2005). *Neural networks in finance: Gaining predictive edge*. United Kingdom: Elsevier Academic Press.
- Plíhal, T. (2016). Granger Causality between Stock Market and Macroeconomic Indicators: Evidence from Germany. *Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis*, 64(6), 2101-2108. Retrieved from https://ideas.repec.org/a/mup/actaun/actaun_2016064062101.html
- Priambodo, B., Rahayu, S., Hazidar, A.-H., Naf'an, E., Masril, M., Handriani, I., . . . Jumaryadi, Y. (2019). Predicting GDP of Indonesia using K-nearest neighbour regression. *Journal of Physics*, 1339. Retrieved from <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1339/1/012040>
- Rodríguez-Vargas, A. (2020). Forecasting Costa Rican inflation with machine learning methods. *American Journal of Central Banking*, 1(1). Retrieved from <https://ideas.repec.org/a/eee/lajcba/v1y2020i1s2666143820300120.html>

- Shareef, H., & Shijin, S. (2017). The term structure of interest rates and macroeconomic factors: Evidence from Indian financial market. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 17(4), 249-256. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S221484501630120X>
- Simonyan, K., Vedaldi, A., & Zisserman, A. (2014). *Deep Inside Convolutional Networks Visualising Image Classification Models and Saliency Maps*. arXiv:1312.6034. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/abs/1312.6034>
- Suhaibu, I., Harvey, S., & Amidu, M. (2017). The impact of monetary policy on stock market performance: Evidence from twelve (12) African countries. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 42, 1372-1382. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0275531916304792>
- Tkacz, G. (2001). Neural network forecasting of canadian GDP growth. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 17(1), 57-69. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0169207000000637>
- Zhao, M., & Chen, J. (2016). Improvement and Comparison of Weighted k Nearest Neighbors Classifiers for Model Selection. *Journal of Software Engineering*, 10(1), 109-118. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/284174726_Improvement_and_Comparison_of_Weighted_k_Nearest_Neighbors_Classifiers_for_Model_Selection

7 Appendices

Table 1.A) Average of Best K vs Horizons Table 1.B) Average of Best K vs Variables

Horizon	KNN	wKNN
1	23	25
3	24	19
6	20	21
Mean	23	22

Variable	KNN	wKNN
EQUITY	21	24
FX	16	22
GDP	24	25
INF	27	17
POLRATE	25	21
Mean	23	22

Table 1.C) Average of Best K vs Countries

Country	KNN	wKNN
BRA	38	38
CHI	17	15
EGP	19	15
IND	22	25
MEX	26	17
SAF	20	15
UK	22	26
US	16	23
Mean	23	22

Table 1 Average of Best K vs Horizons, Variables, and Countries

Variable	Regression	Coeff	P_value	R2
EQUITY	Horizon → K	0.526316	0.753963365	0.002156
EQUITY	K → Test Accuracy	-0.0029	2.04185E-06	0.390713
FX	Horizon → K	-0.88322	0.513870526	0.009322
FX	K → Test Accuracy	0.000203	0.780947804	0.001698
POLRATE	Horizon → K	0.422697	0.853296063	0.000751
POLRATE	K → Test Accuracy	0.001334	0.034356125	0.093694
GDP	Horizon → K	0.776316	0.724623815	0.002724
GDP	K → Test Accuracy	0.000627	0.336039024	0.020133
INF	Horizon → K	-4.10033	0.028743955	0.099767
INF	K → Test Accuracy	-0.00043	0.507466604	0.009608
combined	Horizon → K	-0.65164	0.439426148	0.002514
combined	K → Test Accuracy	-4.2E-05	0.899769024	6.68E-05

Table 2 Regression Results of K vs Horizon and Test Accuracy

Table 3.A) Average Test Accuracy per Variable

Variable	KNN	wKNN	ANN	SVM	LOG	Mean	Sigma	Max
EQUITY	76.17%	73.75%	62.92%	63.25%	61.42%	67.50%	6.90%	76.17%
FX	68.33%	67.92%	59.33%	64.67%	57.33%	63.52%	4.99%	68.33%
GDP	61.75%	61.50%	52.25%	60.08%	53.42%	57.80%	4.60%	61.75%
INF	62.67%	57.00%	50.42%	60.25%	52.42%	56.55%	5.15%	62.67%
POLRATE	57.33%	55.92%	40.33%	54.50%	38.17%	49.25%	9.22%	57.33%
Mean	65.25%	63.22%	53.05%	60.55%	52.55%			
Sigma	7.25%	7.55%	8.75%	3.91%	8.79%			
Max	76.17%	73.75%	62.92%	64.67%	61.42%			

Table 3.B) Average Test Accuracy per Country

Country	KNN	wKNN	ANN	SVM	LOG	Mean	Sigma	Max
BRA	60.67%	57.87%	36.67%	43.87%	36.53%	47.12%	11.52%	60.67%
CHI	66.80%	66.40%	59.60%	61.20%	60.00%	62.80%	3.52%	66.80%
EGP	63.73%	62.13%	46.00%	58.93%	45.60%	55.28%	8.83%	63.73%
IND	66.13%	66.00%	55.73%	62.93%	55.73%	61.31%	5.25%	66.13%
MEX	64.67%	61.60%	59.07%	57.07%	51.07%	58.69%	5.13%	64.67%
SAF	68.67%	61.20%	57.33%	64.27%	63.47%	62.99%	4.16%	68.67%
UK	59.73%	58.00%	47.73%	64.93%	48.93%	55.87%	7.35%	64.93%
US	71.60%	72.53%	62.27%	71.20%	59.07%	67.33%	6.21%	72.53%
Mean	65.25%	63.22%	53.05%	60.55%	52.55%			
Sigma	3.95%	4.90%	8.75%	7.98%	8.84%			
Max	71.60%	72.53%	62.27%	71.20%	63.47%			

Table 3.C) Average Test Accuracy per Horizon

Horizon	KNN	wKNN	ANN	SVM	LOG	Mean	Sigma	Max
1	66.05%	64.75%	52.60%	62.00%	52.95%	59.67%	6.46%	66.05%
3	65.30%	62.85%	52.25%	58.80%	51.85%	58.21%	6.09%	65.30%
6	64.40%	62.05%	54.30%	60.85%	52.85%	58.89%	5.04%	64.40%
Mean	65.25%	63.22%	53.05%	60.55%	52.55%			
Sigma	0.83%	1.39%	1.10%	1.62%	0.61%			
Max	66.05%	64.75%	54.30%	62.00%	52.95%			

Table 3 Average of Test Accuracy per Model

Table 4.A) KNN All Horizons

KNN All Horizons	Target Variable					
Contributing Variable	EQUITY	FX	GDP	INF	POLRATE	Average
LEVEL	16%	15%	25%	32%	22%	22%
SLOPE	14%	13%	9%	15%	16%	13%
CURVATURE	9%	8%	7%	8%	6%	8%
EQUITY	0%	12%	14%	18%	13%	11%
FX	12%	0%	10%	9%	9%	8%
POLRATE	19%	19%	10%	8%	0%	11%
GDP	12%	13%	0%	10%	15%	10%
INF	17%	19%	25%	0%	20%	16%
Max	19%	19%	25%	32%	22%	

Table 4.B) ANN All Horizons

ANN All Horizons	Target Variable					
Contributing Variable	EQUITY	FX	GDP	INF	POLRATE	Average
LEVEL	6%	5%	6%	5%	5%	5%
SLOPE	7%	5%	8%	6%	7%	6%
CURVATURE	8%	6%	7%	8%	5%	7%
EQUITY	0%	25%	18%	21%	24%	18%
FX	15%	0%	17%	19%	17%	13%
POLRATE	26%	16%	20%	18%	0%	16%
GDP	16%	22%	0%	23%	27%	18%
INF	22%	22%	24%	0%	15%	17%
Max	26%	25%	24%	23%	27%	

Table 4.C) SVM All Horizons

SVM All Horizons	Target Variable					
Contributing Variable	EQUITY	FX	GDP	INF	POLRATE	Average
LEVEL	18%	20%	13%	10%	5%	13%
SLOPE	11%	16%	10%	9%	10%	11%
CURVATURE	2%	9%	3%	3%	2%	4%
EQUITY	25%	11%	14%	24%	24%	20%
FX	12%	6%	17%	11%	11%	11%
POLRATE	17%	4%	11%	9%	20%	12%
GDP	7%	8%	7%	10%	8%	8%
INF	9%	26%	26%	23%	19%	21%
Max	25%	26%	26%	24%	24%	

Table 4.D) LOG All Horizons

LOG All Horizons	Target Variable					
Contributing Variable	EQUITY	FX	GDP	INF	POLRATE	Average
LEVEL	20%	7%	9%	9%	5%	10%
SLOPE	5%	5%	8%	8%	6%	6%
CURVATURE	2%	3%	3%	8%	1%	4%
EQUITY	0%	16%	22%	35%	31%	21%
FX	6%	0%	7%	10%	6%	6%
POLRATE	32%	30%	6%	16%	0%	17%
GDP	9%	8%	0%	14%	21%	10%
INF	26%	29%	45%	0%	30%	26%
Max	32%	30%	45%	35%	31%	

Table 4 Feature Importance per Model for all Horizons